

A MODEL FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENT SELF-LEARNING COMPETENCIES IN A CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM

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Annotation: The article makes an attempt to analyze the problems of organizing independent work of students in modern learning conditions and identifies the prospects for work to improve its effectiveness in the conditions of a credit-modular education system. The credit-module organization of the learning process ensures the psychological development of the relationship between teacher and student. These relationships contribute to the development of general educational skills and abilities, in addition, the independence of students in the educational process.

Keywords: independent work, independence, self-study, credit-module system, integration, skills, abilities, education.

Introduction: The credit-modular system, this is the process of organizing training, is a set of modular training technologies and an assessment model based on credit measurement. Carrying it out into a single whole is not only a fruitful process, but also a complex systemic one (Dadakhonova, Z. 2021. pp. 476-480. [4]). In the credit-module principle, importance is attached to two main issues: ensuring independent work of students; assessment of students' knowledge based on ratings.

Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 No. RP-5847 "On approval of the Concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 and the state program for the implementation of the strategy of action in five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, "Year of Science, education and development of the digital economy" 2020. In order to ensure the fulfillment of the tasks defined by decrees No. DP-5953 of March 2, the Cabinet of Ministers adopted a resolution. In accordance with it, starting from the 2020/2021 academic year, a procedure for the gradual transition of the educational process to a credit-module system has been introduced in higher educational institutions of the republic (Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. DP-5349 [1]).

Today's problems of organizing and increasing the efficiency of independent work of university students require constant attention and quality solutions. At the same time, an analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature showed the active beginning of research on the issues of independent learning of students in the mid-20th century; at the beginning of the last century, S.I. Gessen argued that the source of free development is active independent work, and at the same time the source of personal creativity. In addition, the student's personality is created not only by what he writes or speaks, by the actions of his hands, but also by the thoughts, emotions and feelings that he experiences at this time, his desire and volitional actions, as well as his mental state¹. In our opinion, to the activity and independence

¹ Gessen S.I. Fundamentals of Pedagogy. Introduction to Applied Philosophy / Responsible editor and compiler. P. V. Alekseev. —M.: "School-Press", 1995. — 448 p.

of mental work one should once again add their extreme necessity, usefulness and, of course, creative character.

Among the six key positions that must be implemented within the framework of the Bologna process (introducing two-cycle education, monitoring the quality of education, expanding mobility, ensuring the employment of graduates, ensuring the attractiveness of the European education system, an important place is occupied by the requirement to introduce in all national education systems a system for recording the labor intensity of educational work in loans. It is proposed to take the European credit transfer system as a basis.

Modern dynamic life requires the training of specialists who:

- able to quickly adapt to changing life and professional situations, taking into account the analysis of existing problematic issues;
- ready for constant updating of knowledge, self-development, generation of new knowledge, skillful application of knowledge in practice to solve professional problems;
- navigate increasing flows of information, use modern technologies to analyze, transform and apply information in professional activities and their own lives;
- have critical creative thinking;
- sociable, contact-oriented, able to work in different teams;
- are active in achieving their goals.

It is these specialists who can be competitive in the modern labor market, as well as contribute to the competitiveness of their enterprises, institutions and organizations. They will be the ones who will be able to create their own business, adapt to all sorts of changes in the work profile and constantly improve the level of their knowledge, skills and abilities.

Therefore, the higher education system faces the important problem of organizing the educational process of students in the context of the theses expressed. In other words, society sets the task of bringing future specialists to the level of independent navigation in information flows, constant improvement of their knowledge, a creative approach to any changes, unconventional and high-quality solutions to emerging problems, and this is what determines the relevance of this topic.

The ability for further self-learning and self-education is unthinkable without such a personality quality as independence, which in turn is cultivated by independent and only independent activity. Thus, students' independent learning activities should become the leading one. Within the framework of the credit-module education system, in which, in contrast to traditional approaches, a significantly larger amount of independent work of students is assumed, attempts are being actively made to make it truly leading. It is for independent search and development that a large amount of educational material is submitted. There are even additional classes under the guidance of a teacher as part of self-study.

An analysis of scientific research and publications showed that various aspects of organizing students' independent work were studied by such scientists as Yu. Babansky, A. Verbitsky, L. Derkach, V. Kazakov, O. Kirichuk, B. Korotyayev, A. Kucheryavyi, S. Matushkin, A. Moroz, N. Nikandrov, P. Pidkasisty, N. Polovnikova, V. Slastenin, T. Shamova and others. Issues of motivation for students' educational activities were considered by V. Aksenova, T. Gusak, V. Krylova, V. Leontiev, G. Shchukina, V. Vergasov and others. Ways to improve the preparation of students for independent educational activities were analyzed by M. Antonyuk, V. Buryak,

N. Vazheevskaya, L. Derkach, I. Mostovaya, L. Onuchak, M. Soldatenko and others. The modular system of organizing training was studied in detail by A. Aleksyuk, K. Vazina, A. Kucheryavyi, A. Gumenyuk, B. Ognevuyuk, A. Furman , P. Jucevicienė and others. The development of issues related to self-education and self-education of the individual was carried out by N. Bityanova, A. Gromtseva, S. Dneprov, V. Kurinsky, L. Ruvinsky and others. Various aspects of the scientific organization of educational activities were considered in their works by S. Arkhangelsky, Y. Ludchenko and others. Despite the considerable attention of scientists and practitioners to the problem of organizing independent work of university students, important issues that require comprehension and solutions still remain. As Yu. Miroschnichenko and O. Troyan point out, these are undisclosed connections and relationships between the goal of organizing independent work of university students and the methods of its implementation; a holistic theoretical understanding and justification for the organization of independent work of students in the conditions of a credit-modular education system; issues of student motivation in the context of increasing the effectiveness of their own independent educational activities; students mastering rational methods of educational work; developing their skills and abilities for independent educational work (Miroschnichenko Yu., O. Troyan. 2010. P. 60-65. [6]).

In addition, questions about the specific implementation of students' independent work should be added, primarily through modern information and communication technologies. There is research in this direction, but, in our opinion, it is limited to individual subjects (courses), for example, the use of the Internet when studying English in non-core master's programs (Popova N.V. 2010. pp. 305-309. [7]), independent work of students with electronic trainings on the modules of the section "Static Biochemistry" (Bainazarova A. V. 2012. pp. 170-174. [2]), independent work of students in the course of mathematical analysis using MathCAD computer mathematical systems (Temurov S. Yu . 2012. pp. 428-431 [8]) and others.

The purpose of the study is to theoretically substantiate the general didactic conditions for using the credit-modular education system in a higher educational institution and to analyze the state of modern educational programs in a higher educational institution.

Research results.

The credit-module organization of the learning process ensures:

- psychological development of teacher and student, improvement of relations between them;
- contributes to the development of general academic skills and abilities, improving students' independent work skills, allowing them to objectively, taking into account the level of the student's creative approach to planning and performing various kinds of professional tasks;
- evaluate their mastery of the modular program, which includes participation in pedagogical news, discussions during lectures, study of required literature, completion of each creative individual task (development of methods for studying the formation of moral and ethical qualities and traits, modeling of an educational event or educational situation, various forms of training and others);
- keeping notes of primary sources;
- work activity at each practical lesson;
- participation in scientific work (independent processing of a research psychological and pedagogical problem, participation in the development and conduct of an experiment,

generalization of the results obtained, preparation of abstracts with elements of search and research work);

- speaking at a student scientific conference, preparing materials for publication and much more.

The credit-modular system provides two main functions. The first one promotes the mobility of students and teachers and simplifies the transition from one university to another. The second is accumulative, a clear definition of the volume of work carried out by the student, taking into account all types of educational and scientific activities. Let us consider the implementation of the second function in the practice of higher education institutions. Many higher educational institutions in Uzbekistan operate under the credit-modular system, and the majority of respondents have a positive attitude towards this system. However, in our opinion, the most relevant at this stage of the introduction of the credit system of education in higher educational institutions is the problem of effectively organizing independent work, instilling in students the need to constantly independently work to improve the quality of knowledge, improve professional skills. The main indicators of a student's level of preparedness for independent work can be:

- the ability to plan one's activities, see variable ways to achieve a goal and find the optimal one, proficiency in speed reading;
- the ability to highlight the main idea in the information received;
- skills in a compact, abbreviated presentation of the information you own;
- ability to perform various types of recording of received information (abstracts, extracts, citations, etc.);
- compliance with bibliography requirements, etc.

Independent work of a student involves activities that he performs without the direct participation of the teacher, but on his instructions, under his leadership, supervision, and control. Organization of independent work on any subject should be aimed at solving two interrelated problems:

1. To develop students' independence in cognitive activity, that is, to teach them to independently acquire knowledge;
2. Teach students to independently use knowledge in learning and practical activities.

The organization and control of students' independent work, as experience has shown, makes it possible to successfully resolve issues related to improving the preparation of a highly educated individual who is capable of systematically replenishing their knowledge, which ensures:

- reduction of adaptation time for first-year students;
- streamlining independent work, daily routine, creating the most favorable conditions for the harmonious development of the individual;
- reducing the number of cases of untimely completion of educational assignments by students and improving their quality;
- wider involvement of students in public events and research work;
- formation of the need for constant self-education;
- improving academic performance and quality of education.

Successful resolution of these issues is possible subject to the use of scientifically based organization of independent work of students, which also involves the creation of an optimal system for monitoring knowledge, skills and abilities.

Having analyzed the specifics of higher educational institutions using the credit-module education system, we can come to the conclusion that today favorable conditions have not yet been created for the introduction of the credit-module education system in our country. To solve this problem, the following conditions are necessary in higher education institutions:

1. Creation of a regulatory framework in all educational institutions of the country;
2. Availability of sufficient material and technical base in each educational institution;
3. Development of methodology, methods and methods for the effective implementation of a credit-module training system;
4. Improving the infrastructure of the education system and its management mechanisms.

Conclusion: Thus, for the successful introduction of a credit-modular system of training organization in higher educational institutions, it is necessary, first of all, to solve the problems of organizing and conducting independent work.

We see prospects for improving the effectiveness of the application of the credit-modular training system in the development of new programs, also in interactivity, in the flexible and individual use of materials and, of course, in the proper training of teaching staff in higher educational institutions of the country.

Further research is expected to be carried out in the direction of studying other problems of organizing students' independent work in training using the credit-module system.

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